

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Ergasheva Guli Buranovna

**THE WAYS TO REFLECT AFFECTIVE EMOTIONS (ANGER, JOY, HORROR,
ADMIRATION) AND THEIR EXPRESSION IN LITERARY TEXTS**

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/FEVRAL

